

Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Action Strategy: Results and Prospects

Yuldashev Qodirjon Mamadjanovich¹, Soliev Ibodulloxon Ismatullaevich², Nurdinova Shoiraxon Rashidkhonovna³, Bobaev Isroiljon Abdinabievich⁴

¹Namangan Institute of Engineering Technology, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

²Namangan State University, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor

³Namangan State University, PhD teacher of the Department of Economics

⁴Namangan State University, 5 A 230102 Specialty "Economics" (by industries and sectors)

1st year MIQT BU 20th group master

ANNOTATION: The article discusses the measures for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan and the further facilitation of the business environment for the free activities of entrepreneurs.

KEYWORDS: ATM 24/7 Online booths, "Every family is an entrepreneur" program, 14% soft loans provided to individuals and citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan on the basis of the State program, entrepreneurship, Business, Entrepreneur, capital, land, means of production, entrepreneurship activities, manager, business school, business plan, goods and services.

INTRODUCTION

The development of small business and private entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan and the state regulation of this sector are becoming more active. The ever-expanding business environment in our country leads to the provision of incentives for small businesses, the number of business entities in almost all sectors, engaged in entrepreneurial activities is growing day by day. One of the directions of deepening economic reforms in Uzbekistan is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. The leading role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the national economy will ultimately serve to increase the country's gross domestic product by employing a significant part of the labor force.

The development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the period 2017-2021 at five priority strategies in the direction of the economy, reduce the participation of the Vltava, the protection of private property rights and its priority to further strengthen the position of small business and private entrepreneurship, the development of institutional and structural reforms continue to pay special attention to the issues of q focuses on. [1].

The creation of a legal framework for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the national economy, including the existence of relevant legislation. The application of tax benefits, the introduction of soft loans and their legal protection is clearly reflected in the activities of small businesses.

The establishment in our country of a representative (business ombudsman) for the protection of the rights and legitimate interests of business entities under the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan has played an important role in the development of their activities. [2].

An important factor in the development of small business and private entrepreneurship is the problem of financing this sector. By positively addressing this problem, the role of the private sector in the sustainable development of the country's economy will increase.

Although the pace of development of small business and private entrepreneurship has been stable in recent years, the scale of these enterprises is small. In most cases, although these enterprises have a certain position in the market, they face the problem of lack of financial resources to expand production. This problem, in our opinion, is due, on the one hand, to the general shortage

Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Action Strategy: Results and Prospects

of financial resources in the country, and, on the other hand, to the fact that private sector entrepreneurs often do not have the skills to participate in the financial market.

Small businesses and private entrepreneurs often face a number of challenges due to lack of start-up capital. In our opinion, the guarantee provided by law is also provided by legal entities and individuals with the ability to pay, as well as citizens' self-government bodies. Collateral, withholding, guarantee, advance payment, etc. can also be used to attract start-up capital. At the same time, a business entity may use its property, including property and property rights, to insure its obligations under credit agreements, as well as its insurance policy on the risk of default on the loan.

In accordance with a number of normative and legal acts adopted in our country, various benefits and conveniences have been provided for small business and private entrepreneurship, the system of preferential lending has been simplified. The introduction of a public-private partnership mechanism to ensure the development of the private sector contributes to the development of this sector. [3].

The proclamation of 2020 as the Year of Science, Enlightenment and Development of the Digital Economy by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M.Mirziyoev, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship during the coronavirus pandemic with the help of ICT (information and communication technologies) the ability to exchange documents with each other remotely without the use of the Internet has been set up online. Such conditions have created a number of conveniences for entrepreneurs to send monthly tax returns online to the tax authorities. In addition, at the initiative of the President, DXM (Public Service Centers) were launched in cities and districts of each region of the country, where all entrepreneurs were issued their personal EDS (Electronic Digital Signature), saving time and money on invoices for goods and services. Created the ability to send e-mail in an instant. In addition, mobile applications have been created by commercial banks located in the regions of the Republic. This provided the bank's customers with the opportunity to use high-quality and fast banking services remotely. Now every customer of commercial banks can get a loan and pay for a loan without leaving home via mobile applications, transactions on bank plastic cards from card to card, opening deposits, international money transfers, utility payments, mobile operators in Uzbekistan (Ucell, All residents of the country have the opportunity to make payments to Beeline, Uzmobil, MobiUZ, Internet providers without leaving home. In addition, each commercial bank has installed ATMs for cash withdrawals from Uzcard and Humo bank plastic cards in all regions of the **country**, and launched **ATM 24/7 Online booths** of each commercial bank . The main goal is to alleviate the burden of our people, meet their demand for cash and ensure their financial stability.

In fact, the main purpose of such reforms is to further develop the way of life of our people, to financially support their living conditions. Today in our country, great attention is paid to the issues of state regulation of small business and private entrepreneurship using modern ICT, the development of the business environment in every family. Citizens living in the meeting of the Railway book superior to low-income segments of the population by commercial banks on the basis of **the State program "family business" 14% of soft loans** , MFY individuals who engaged in sewing marked with a special certificate course, the citizens of the commercial banks provided for the allocation of soft loans. Such benefits provided by the state and the system of operation of commercial banks "Mahallabay" are aimed at financial support of citizens registered in the women's register, the reduction of poverty in their families.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

As a result of the research, the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the regions, the role and importance of small businesses in the employment of the population and the production of gross regional product were studied. The study examines the state of development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the regions through the use of methods such as economic analysis, comparison, observation, questionnaires, comparisons, systematic analysis. Scientific conclusions and proposals for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship have been developed in our country.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the main factors in the development of the economy in the context of market relations is the development of small business and private entrepreneurship. The modern meaning of the concepts of small business and private entrepreneurship was first used by the English economist Richard Cantillon in the late seventeenth and early eighteenth centuries. In his opinion, an entrepreneur is a person who acts in order to make a profit in a risky environment. He therefore saw the land and the labor factor as the source of wealth that determined economic prosperity. Later, in the late eighteenth and early nineteenth centuries, the famous French economist J.B. Sey (1767-1832)

The Booklet of Political Economy described three factors of productive entrepreneurial activity: land, capital, and the integrity of labor.

Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Action Strategy: Results and Prospects

At the turn of the XIX - XX centuries, many began to understand the importance and role of the institution of entrepreneurship. The French economist Andre Marsh all (1907-1968) was the first to add a fourth factor to the three factors of production (land, capital, labor) - the organizational factor. Since then, the concept of entrepreneurship and the scope of work in this area is expanding. The American economist J.B. Park (1847-1938) made some changes to J.B. Say's "trinity formula." According to him, four factors are always involved in production:

1. Capital;
 2. Means of production and land;
 3. Entrepreneurial activity;
 4. Labor
- The American scientist R. Heatherrich said, "Tad entrepreneurship is the process of creating something new that has its value, and the entrepreneur spends all the time and day to do so, taking all the financial, psychological and social risks and rewarding them with money and money. a person who is satisfied with what he has achieved . "

A. Hoskin, a British professor, explains that " a person who runs the business at his own expense, is personally involved in the management of the business and has a personal responsibility to provide the necessary tools, an independent decision-maker is an individual entrepreneur."

The third stage of entrepreneurship is the individual characteristics of entrepreneurship: 1. The ability to find the right way to change the economic and social situation; 2. Independence in the selection and decision-making of management; 3. It is characterized by the full manifestation of management skills.

The current stage in the development of business theory can be included in the fourth stage. Its emergence is associated with its transfer to the management aspect in the analysis of entrepreneurial behavior. This means that the analysis of business problems in theory is now carried out within the framework of many interdependent disciplines.

Thus, **entrepreneurship** is a special type of economic activity, which is based on risk-based independent initiative, responsibility, activity based on entrepreneurial activity , aimed at achieving more goals at a lower cost and in the future. This foreign countries, the term "**Business**", which is the modern name for the country , "BUSINESS" will be called. It is no exaggeration to say that this term has become ingrained in the minds of our working people. In this regard, the terms "**BUSINESSMAN**" are very popular in foreign countries, and in our country - **BUSINESSMEN** .

Entrepreneurship is a special type of economic activity, the empty stage of which is usually associated with the activity of thinking or its result, only then it takes on a material form.

The main goal of the entrepreneur is to determine the need for the product in order to have its own consumers. An entrepreneur should take into account the following key factors in shaping his customers:

- The novelty of the product and its relevance to the interests of the buyer;
- Quality of goods or services;
- Price of goods or services;
- the commodity level of universality;
- Appearance of the product, its compliance with customer requirements;
- Access to after-sales service;
- Compliance of the goods with accepted general or state standards;
- Attractiveness of advertising of goods and services, attracting the attention of the buyer, etc .;

The personal qualities, abilities, capabilities and job qualities of an entrepreneur will be the driving force of entrepreneurship. Entrepreneurial job qualities should be based on the following principles:

First, the market's place in the economic system through the analysis of the level of supply of goods and services;

Second, the ability to prepare to create a personal production structure;

Third, to carry out initial business calculations based on the results of marketing research;

Fourth, the ability to set the right direction in the implementation of an entrepreneurial project;

Fifth, to be the first to implement a new technological idea and to be able to imagine how the end result, product or service can be obtained from this idea in practice.

Another important feature of entrepreneurship is the ability to anticipate how decisions will be made by the market in the implementation of new ideas in the production process. From this point of view, the introduction of innovation in the market and the ability to combine consumer response into a single process is the key to entrepreneurial success.

In today's context, **the** concept of "**entrepreneur**" is very close to the concept of "**manager**". However, if the entrepreneur is the owner, the manager is the manager. In practice, however, most owners act as managers, and a number of managers continue to

Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Action Strategy: Results and Prospects

own the manufacturing enterprises they manage. Of course, managers in this case need modern equipment, technology and skilled workers in their enterprises. First of all, the company pays special attention to the quality of the product, reducing production and unforeseen costs in order to achieve high profits in the future, and advertise these products under the logo of their enterprises in the media (Facebook), Facebook and Instagram. Telegrams should be reflected on social networks. In this case, managers receive loans from commercial banks on the basis of a well-thought-out **business plan** for the purchase of equipment for the production of quality products in order to develop their production. The main goal is to ensure that managers export quality products produced by their enterprises to foreign countries and ensure that their products occupy the world market.

The concept of "**entrepreneurship**" is defined in the encyclopedic dictionary of the entrepreneur as follows.

Entrepreneurship - (from the English word entrepreneurship) is an independent activity of citizens aimed at personal income, profit. This activity is carried out on its own behalf, in exchange for property liability and legal liability of the legal entity. Entrepreneur (from the English word, entrepreneur) can engage in all economic activities not prohibited by law, including brokerage, purchasing, consulting, dealing in securities.

Economic, social, legal and other specific conditions must be created for the formation of entrepreneurship. Economic conditions include: supply and demand for a good, the availability of the amount of money a buyer needs to buy, the surplus or shortage of jobs, the labor force, which affects the wages of workers, i.e., purchasing power. The availability and access to cash resources, the amount of return on capital invested, and the amount of credit that can be obtained to finance their business operations affect economic conditions. In the formation of entrepreneurial activity, it is important to address the issues of training, retraining and advanced training of business personnel. To do this, organize the study of modern methods of doing business, training and retraining of employees, sending them to developed countries for training, training and retraining of teachers for business training, opening of advisory centers for the selection of employees for the entrepreneurial sector need This is in order to ensure the implementation of the reforms, **the founder of the Russian businessman UMS Holding multimillarder Alisher Usmanov**, the city of Namangan, Amir Temur Street, the former "Little Garden" at 6 hectares, agar **International Business Center** will begin construction in the spring of 2021. This business center includes Congress Hall, Business High School, Hotel, Ecopark, Sports and Health Facilities.

(Sport comp lexes), artificial lakes (Artificial lakes), fountains (Fountains), parking lots (Auto parkings) will be built and put into operation. At the Business School of this International Business Center, young people interested in all areas of business in Namangan region can study and start their own business independently in the future. **(Figure 1)**

Figure 1. International business center of multimillionaire compatriot Alisher Usmanov, founder of Uzbek entrepreneur UMS Holding

Every business activity takes place in an appropriate legal environment. Therefore, it is important to create the necessary legal conditions. This is primarily due to the existence of decrees regulating business and laws that create favorable conditions for business development, ie the short and simple process of registration of enterprises, protection of entrepreneurship from state

Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Action Strategy: Results and Prospects

bureaucracy, improvement of tax legislation and reduction of tax rates. Development of cooperation . Currently, a two-year tax for private entrepreneurs who have just passed the state registration and started a new business in the Republic

Figure 2. The share of small business and private entrepreneurship in GRP in Tashkent region

It is no exaggeration to say that a favorable business environment has been created for them to engage in small business and private entrepreneurship in our country.

The comprehensive measures taken to further improve the business environment in Uzbekistan allow small business and private entrepreneurship to ensure rapid development and sustainable economic growth. For example, in Tashkent region, the share of small business and private entrepreneurship in GRP increased from 34.0% to 52.7% and increased by 18.7% from 200 to 2019 (Figure 2).

As a result of the measures taken to support small businesses and private entrepreneurship and create favorable conditions for them, their number is growing every year. As of January 1, 2020, the number of small businesses operating in Tashkent region (excluding farmers) amounted to 32,602, which is 24,828 or 4.19 times more than in 2000. (Figure 3). As of January 1, 2020, 9576 small businesses were engaged in trade, 7455 in industry, 2960 in construction, 4139 in agriculture and forestry , 2896 in housing and food.

Figure 3. Number of small businesses operating in Tashkent region (as of January 1, 2020 in thousands)

Development of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship Action Strategy: Results and Prospects

427 in the field of information and communication, 507 in the field of health and social services, 1292 in the field of transportation and storage, 3350 in other areas. (Figure 4)

Figure 4 Distribution of the number of small businesses operating in Tashkent region by type of economic activity as of January 1, 2020

The share of small business in the number of people employed in the economy is 78.0 percent in Japan, 71.0 percent in Italy, 69.5 percent in Germany, 56.0 percent in the United Kingdom, 54.0 percent in the United States, and 25 percent in Russia. , We can see that it is 6 percent (Figure 5).

Figure 5. The share of small business in the total number of people employed in the economy in different countries of the world

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

If we talk about the role of small business and private entrepreneurship in the development of key sectors of the economy, it is necessary to ensure a competitive environment in the economy, supply products to large enterprises, create new jobs, increase market flexibility, mobilize resources, increase tax revenues. Security is determined by factors such as the steady increase in the level of income of the population. Small business and private entrepreneurship are one of the key factors in filling our domestic market with competitive and quality products, providing employment and increasing incomes and welfare.

Based on the above, it can be said that the number of small and medium-sized businesses is growing every year as a result of measures taken to support them and create favorable conditions for them. Such measures also play a special role in ensuring employment and preventing poverty. The comprehensive measures being taken to further improve the business environment in Uzbekistan allow for the rapid development of small business and private entrepreneurship and sustainable economic growth.

REFERENCES

- 1) **Mirziyoev same period** . Address of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan to the Oliy Majlis. People's Word newspaper. December 29, 2018,. № 271-272 (7229-7230)
- 2) On the strategy of actions for further development of the Republic of Uzbekistan . February 7, 2017, No. PF-4947. National Database of Legislation, 31.07.2018, 06/18/5483/1594.
- 3) Yuldashev K, Kholmiraev A Improving the implementation of the mechanism of private partnership in Uzbekistan. "Young Scientist " № 51 (289) pp-435.
- 4) A.Abdullaev, K.Muftaydinov "Small business management" Tashkent, Finance edition 2003, 192 pages
- 5) A.Samadov, G.Ostanaqulova "Small business and entrepreneurship", Tashkent, Finance and Economics edition 2008
- 6) T.Malikov, N.Khaydarov, "Finance: It is public finance", Tashkent, Economic Finance edition 2009
- 7) E.Egamberdiev, H.Khojakulov "Small business and entrepreneurship" Tashkent, "Manaviyat" edition 2003
- 8) V.Khodiev, M.Kasimova A.Samadov "Small business and private entrepreneurship" Tashkent, Tashkent State University of Economics, 2010
- 9) Рашидов, Р. (2017). НЕКОТОРЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ ЭФФЕКТИВНОГО ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ТЕХНИКИ В ХЛОПКОВОДСТВЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ. *Общество и экономика*, (3-4), 138-141.
- 10) Alojnovich, R. R. (2016). Correlation between resource economy factors in cotton growing. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (6 (7)).
- 11) Rahmatullo, R. (2016). Sectoral specificities by application of resource saving technology in cotton growing. *Economics*, (8 (17)).
- 12) Rashidov, R. (2016). Correlation between resource economy factors in cotton growing. *Наука и образование сегодня*, (6), 68-70.
- 13) Alojnovich, R. R. (2019). Economic efficiency of resource-saving technologies in the cotton industry system of indicators. *International Journal of Scientific and Technology Research*, 8(11), 3861-3863.
- 14) <http://www.ijstr.org/final-print/nov2019/Economic-Efficiency-Of-Resource-saving-Technologies-In-The-Cotton-Industry-System-Of-Indicators-.pdf>
- 15) Zulfqarova Dilfuza Gulomjanovna, Saidboev Shermirza Dotkamirzaevich, Rashidov Rahmatullo Alojnovich "Conceptual Bases of Full Realization of Women's Labour and Entrepreneurial Activity". *PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION* (2021) 58(2): 237-240
- 16) <http://www.psychologyandeducation.net/pae/index.php/pae/article/view/1552>
- 17) Gulomjanovna, Z. D., Dotkamirzaevich, S. S., & Alojnovich, R. R. (2021). Conceptual Bases of Full Realization of Women's Labour and Entrepreneurial Activity. *Psychology and Education Journal*, 58(2), 237-240.
- 18) Alojnovich, R. R., & Sardorbek, O. (2021). THEORETICAL BASES OF INCREASE OF ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF USE OF RESOURCESAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN THE COTTON INDUSTRY. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(ICDSIL), 5-5.
- 19) Tursunaliyevich, A. Z., & Alojnovich, R. R. (2021). CREATION OF ELECTRONIC TEXTBOOKS IN HIGHER EDUCATION. *International Engineering Journal For Research & Development*, 6(ICDSIL), 4-4.
- 20) ALOJONOVICH, R. R. (2021). RESOURCE-SAVING TECHNOLOGIES IN COTTON-GROWING ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY INDICATOR SYSTEMS. *PLANT CELL BIOTECHNOLOGY AND MOLECULAR BIOLOGY*, 134-140.
- 21) <https://ikpress.org/index.php/PCBMB/article/view/5943>

Internet information

- 1) www.ziyonet.uz information on the subject of eating
- 2) Data and economic and statistical analysis on the development of small business and private entrepreneurship in the Tashkent region of the Statistics Department of the Tashkent region through the website <http://toshvilstat.uz/index.php/uz/>
- 3) www.stat.uz information on the subject of eating